

**ENABLING
ENVIRONMENTS
FOR DATA
PRIVACY AND
INNOVATION**

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AS DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES INCREASINGLY SHAPE THE FUTURE OF FOOD AND NUTRITION SYSTEMS, QUESTIONS OF DATA OWNERSHIP, USER TRUST, AND INCLUSIVE DESIGN HAVE BECOME MORE URGENT THAN EVER.

Digital services—from personalised nutrition apps to data-sharing platforms—rely heavily on the collection and use of consumer data. Yet, ensuring that individuals remain in control of their data, that systems are designed with users in mind, and that technologies support meaningful societal benefits require deliberate action. The FOODITY project addresses these challenges by exploring how data-driven innovation can align with principles of data sovereignty, inclusion, and transparency.

Based on collaborative work with pilot beneficiaries and stakeholders, this brochure compiles practical recommendations across four key areas.

DATA SOVEREIGNTY AND TRUST

Consumers must have clear control over their personal data. The study recommends privacy-by-design approaches, transparent consent mechanisms, and personal data spaces to strengthen trust and user autonomy. These elements are essential for building ethical, human-centred digital ecosystems.

INCLUSIVE APP DEVELOPMENT

Inclusive design begins with early and continuous engagement. Recommendations emphasise co-creation with users, regular feedback loops, and inclusive communication to ensure digital tools reflect real-world needs and are accessible to diverse communities.

DATA-BASED NUTRITION SYSTEMS AND DATA SHARING PRACTICES

Responsible and effective data use requires strong technical foundations. The study promotes the use of interoperable systems, consent management tools, and open data standards to enable secure, transparent, and meaningful data sharing across services and stakeholders.

POLICY ACTIONS

Enabling frameworks are needed to support ethical digital transformation. Recommendations include policy support for data sovereignty, investment in open and interoperable infrastructures, and regulatory clarity to foster innovation while protecting individual rights.

Together, these recommendations offer a roadmap for building responsible, inclusive, and user-driven digital food systems, ensuring that data works for people, not the other way around.

WHO SHOULD READ THIS?

This brochure is designed for two key audiences whose collaboration is essential for advancing trustworthy, inclusive, and innovative digital solutions

Developers and Innovators of Digital Solutions

WHO THEY ARE

App developers, IT specialists, tech startups, and research consortia building digital food and nutrition platforms.

WHY IT MATTERS

They are responsible for designing systems that respect data sovereignty, user trust, and accessibility, while meeting scientific and ethical standards.

WHAT THEY NEED

Clear policy frameworks, usability benchmarks, interoperability guidelines, and funding for participatory and evidence-based innovation.

Policy Makers and Regulatory Authorities

WHO THEY ARE

Government agencies, EU and national regulators, ministries, and funding bodies.

WHY IT MATTERS

They set the legal, financial, and ethical frameworks that enable (or hinder) trustworthy digital innovation.

WHAT THEY NEED

Evidence of best practices, policy tools to enforce data protection and inclusivity, and insights into how regulation can foster innovation while safeguarding citizens.

FROM RESEARCH TO PRACTICE

The following recommendations were collaboratively developed together with FOODITY-supported start-up teams. Drawing on their hands-on experiences, we cross-checked these insights with academic literature and further validated them through practical expertise from the field. This was a continuous process of research, dialogue, and reflection. The approach culminated in an interactive online workshop, where participants worked together to refine and target the recommendations. All key outcomes of this process are concisely summarised in the following section.

RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR DATA SOVEREIGNTY AND TRUST

Ensuring data sovereignty and trust is key to empowering users in the digital space.

These recommendations highlight practical ways to give people real control over their data, strengthen transparency, and create systems that balance privacy with meaningful participation.

ENABLE CONTROL OVER PERSONAL DATA

Allow users to view, edit, delete, and transfer their data. Co-create intuitive control features with users and provide tutorials.

ENSURE TRANSPARENCY AND INFORMED CONSENT

Replace legal jargon with clear explanations of data use. Make consent processes easy to understand and reverse.

SUPPORT REVERSIBILITY AND DATA PORTABILITY

Enable users to withdraw permissions and export their data without barriers. Design systems that prevent vendor lock-in.

PROTECT AGAINST DATA MISUSE WITH STRONG SAFEGUARDS

Use encryption, anonymization, and robust security policies to protect sensitive data.

RAISE AWARENESS OF DATA RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Include awareness-building elements during development and in-app experiences to empower users to exercise their data rights.

ENABLE PARTICIPATION IN DATA GOVERNANCE

Involve users in co-creating governance models and terms of service, ensuring their values are reflected in data practices.

BALANCE DATA SHARING AND PRIVACY WITH CLEAR OPTIONS

Offer customisable privacy settings and only collect what is strictly necessary. Communicate clearly how data will be used.

FOSTER TRUST THROUGH RESPECTFUL ENGAGEMENT

Build trust through transparency, ongoing communication, and collaborations with trusted intermediaries like doctors.

ANCHOR DEVELOPMENT IN LEGAL AND ETHICAL FRAMEWORKS

Ensure compliance with regulations like GDPR and make legal rights accessible and actionable for users.

DESIGN FOR DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY ACROSS ALL USER GROUPS

Develop inclusive interfaces that support autonomy across diverse populations, including older adults and people with low digital literacy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR INCLUSIVE APP DEVELOPMENT

Effective digital solutions are built around the real needs of their users.

These recommendations provide guidance for creating tools that are practical, accessible, trustworthy, and adaptable across diverse contexts.

START WITH REAL USERS

Engage users early and continuously in the development process to ensure the solution meets real needs and fosters motivation.

INCLUDE RELATED PROFESSIONALS IN DEVELOPMENT

Involve experts to ensure relevance. Partnering with related institutions, e.g. hospitals, restaurants, shops etc. gives access to target groups and adds credibility.

CLEARLY DEFINE AND UNDERSTAND YOUR TARGET GROUP

Use market analysis and needs assessments to deeply understand user characteristics, behaviours, and motivations.

ENSURE SIMPLE, FAST, AND PRIVACY-RESPECTING UX

Design intuitive interfaces that require minimal registration and only collect essential data, reducing entry barriers and enhancing user trust.

ACCOUNT FOR THE NEEDS OF ELDERLY OR LESS TECH-SAVVY USERS

Use high-contrast visuals, large fonts, simplified navigation, and co-creation to ensure accessibility.

TEST IN REAL-LIFE SCENARIOS

Pilot test in real contexts to validate functionality and user experience, ideally using a control group.

USE INCENTIVES TO MAINTAIN ENGAGEMENT

Incorporate gamification or rewards to motivate consistent use and daily data entry.

BUILD FLEXIBILITY INTO PROJECT PLANNING

Use project management tools for coordinating external stakeholders and always prepare a backup timeline.

BASE THE APP ON SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE

Ensure that content and features are grounded in validated research and make this information visible to users to build credibility.

RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR DATA BASED NUTRITION SYSTEMS AND DATA SHARING PRACTICES

Well-designed nutrition systems rely on accurate, user-centred data and transparent sharing practices.

These recommendations outline how to build secure, accessible, and adaptable solutions that balance legal compliance, usability, and meaningful personalisation.

GATHER COMPREHENSIVE USER DATA BEFORE DEVELOPMENT

Collect detailed information on users' age, language, and digital literacy to inform the structure, logic, and personalisation of the nutrition system.

ENSURE GDPR-COMPLIANT DATA SOVEREIGNTY THROUGH USER-FRIENDLY DESIGN

Build privacy features that meet legal requirements while remaining accessible. Interfaces should make it easy for users to control, understand, and manage their data.

ENABLE NATIVE INTEGRATION WITH COMMON CLOUD SERVICES

Ensure that external tools can be seamlessly integrated into infrastructures like Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, or Gaia-X. Avoid reliance on redirections or siloed services that disrupt user experience.

ALLOW MULTIPLE INPUT FORMATS TO IMPROVE ACCESSIBILITY AND DATA ACCURACY

Support various data input types such as multiple-choice, numeric fields, and open text. Design with multilingual and accessible interfaces to accommodate diverse users.

GUIDE USERS TO PROVIDE HIGH-QUALITY DATA

Integrate prompts, tutorials, and instructional text to help users enter accurate, complete, and relevant data.

DESIGN THE SYSTEM BASED ON REAL USER DATA

Use insights from collected user data to drive system design and iteration. Avoid pre-defined models; let real usage patterns guide feature development.

PROVIDE CLEAR DEVELOPER DOCUMENTATION AND INTEGRATION SUPPORT

Accompany all external components with up-to-date technical documentation and integration guidelines to minimise friction and reduce onboarding time for development teams.

PLAN FOR TECHNICAL COMPLEXITY AND ALLOW SUFFICIENT TIME FOR INTEGRATION

Recognise that integrating third-party or modular tools may require more time than expected. Build flexibility into project timelines for troubleshooting and adaptation.

ENSURE ALL TEAM MEMBERS ARE GDPR-AWARE AND ALIGNED

Equip the interdisciplinary team, with a shared understanding of GDPR responsibilities to maintain compliance across all development stages.

TAILOR OUTREACH AND RECRUITMENT STRATEGIES TO SPECIFIC TARGET GROUPS

Allocate time and resources to develop project-specific strategies for reaching and involving the intended user base. Customise outreach methods based on demographic and cultural profiles.

KEY POLICY ACTIONS

FOR DATA SOVEREIGNTY, TRUST, AND INCLUSIVE DIGITAL SOLUTIONS

Clear policy measures are needed to make digital systems trustworthy, secure, and accessible to all.

These recommendations point out essential steps for current practice and provide a solid basis for future developments.

GUARANTEE USER CONTROL AND DATA PORTABILITY

Mandate systems that allow citizens to view, edit, delete, and transfer their personal data easily, ensuring reversibility and protection against vendor lock-in.

ENFORCE TRANSPARENCY AND INFORMED CONSENT

Require simple, jargon-free explanations of data use, with consent processes that are easy to understand, revoke, and adapt over time.

STRENGTHEN DATA PROTECTION SAFEGUARDS

Implement strict security standards (e.g., encryption, anonymization, GDPR compliance) to protect sensitive food and nutrition data from misuse.

PROMOTE INCLUSIVE AND ACCESSIBLE DIGITAL SOLUTIONS

Set accessibility standards ensuring digital apps work for older adults, people with low digital literacy, and diverse user groups through co-design, clear navigation, and multilingual options.

INSTITUTIONALISE USER PARTICIPATION IN DATA GOVERNANCE

Develop frameworks for involving citizens, consumers, and professionals in shaping governance models, terms of service, and ethical standards for digital systems.

SUPPORT EVIDENCE-BASED AND TRUSTWORTHY INNOVATION

Require that digital tools be grounded in validated scientific evidence, pilot-tested in real-life contexts, and transparently communicate their evidence base to users.

BUILD CAPACITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY ACROSS STAKEHOLDERS

Ensure interdisciplinary teams are trained in GDPR and ethical data use, with clear accountability for compliance and user trust.

These actionable insights are grounded in a comprehensive study that brought together evidence from literature, the perspectives of experts, and the experiences of digital innovators through an interdisciplinary workshop.

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